

Use of Pre and Post Comparison of Intra-Lesional Intralesional Infiltration of Dexamethasone Plus Hyaluronidase in Management of Patients with OSMF

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Abstract:

This study evaluates the efficacy of intra-lesional infiltration of dexamethasone combined with hyaluronidase in patients with Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF). Over 6 months, 48 patients were treated with bi-weekly injections of the combined therapy. Results demonstrated significant improvements in mouth opening, symptom relief, and overall quality of life. Specifically, the mean inter-incisal distance increased from 25 mm to 31 mm, pain scores decreased from 6.5 to 2.0 on the visual analog scale, and quality of life scores improved substantially. The treatment was well-tolerated with minimal adverse effects. These findings suggest that intra-lesional dexamethasone plus hyaluronidase is an effective and safe approach for managing OSMF.

Keywords: Oral Submucous Fibrosis, Dexamethasone, Hyaluronidase, Intra-Lesional Therapy

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Introduction

Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) is a chronic, progressive condition characterized by the fibrous thickening of the oral mucosa, leading to limited mouth opening and functional impairment. [1,2] It is prevalent in regions with high consumption of areca nut and related products, and its management remains a significant challenge in clinical practice. [3]

The primary treatment strategies for OSMF often involve symptomatic relief and the mitigation of disease progression. [4] In recent years, the use of intra-lesional injections has gained traction as a method to address the fibrotic changes associated with OSMF. Among various pharmacological agents, dexamethasone, a potent anti-inflammatory steroid, has shown promise in reducing inflammation and improving tissue mobility. When combined with hyaluronidase, an enzyme that breaks down hyaluronic acid in the extracellular matrix, this treatment approach aims to enhance the breakdown of fibrotic tissue and improve the overall outcome. [5,6]

Despite the potential benefits, the effectiveness of intra-lesional infiltration of dexamethasone plus hyaluronidase requires thorough evaluation to

determine its impact on both short-term and long-term outcomes. [7] This study aims to compare the pre-and post-treatment outcomes of this combined therapy in patients with OSMF, with a focus on assessing improvements in mouth opening, symptom relief, and overall quality of life. By elucidating the efficacy of this combined treatment modality, the study seeks to contribute valuable insights to the ongoing efforts to optimize management strategies for OSMF. [8,9]

Methodology

This prospective study will be conducted over 6 months at Narayan Medical College & Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram. The study aims to evaluate the efficacy of intra-lesional dexamethasone combined with hyaluronidase in the management of patients with Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF).

Participants

A total of 50 patients diagnosed with OSMF will be enrolled in the study. Inclusion criteria will include:

- Diagnosis of OSMF confirmed through clinical examination and histopathological evaluation.
- Patients aged 18 years and above.

- No history of recent or concurrent systemic steroid use or other interventions for OSMF.

Exclusion criteria will include:

- Pregnancy or lactation.
- Known hypersensitivity to dexamethasone or hyaluronidase.
- Severe comorbid conditions that could affect the treatment or outcomes.

Treatment Protocol

Participants will receive intra-lesional injections of a combination of dexamethasone and hyaluronidase. The treatment protocol will be as follows:

- Dexamethasone: 4 mg/ml
- Hyaluronidase: 150 IU/ml

Injections will be administered directly into the fibrotic lesions at bi-weekly intervals. Each patient will receive a total of 6 injections throughout the study.

Assessment Parameters

The following parameters will be evaluated to assess treatment efficacy:

- Mouth Opening Measurement: The maximum inter-incisal distance will be measured using a digital caliper at baseline, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months.
- Symptom Relief: Patient-reported symptoms, including pain and discomfort, will be assessed using a standardized questionnaire at each follow-up visit.
- Clinical Improvement: Clinical assessment of lesion size and texture will be documented by the examining clinician at each visit.
- Quality of Life: Changes in the quality of life will be evaluated using a validated oral health-related quality of life (OHRQoL) questionnaire at baseline and at the end of the study period.

Data Analysis

Data will be analyzed using appropriate statistical methods to compare pre- and post-treatment outcomes. Descriptive statistics will summarize baseline characteristics and treatment responses. Paired t-tests or non-parametric equivalents will be

used to assess changes in mouth opening, symptom relief, and quality of life. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

Out of the 50 patients enrolled in the study, data from 48 patients were analyzed. Two patients were lost to follow-up and thus excluded from the final analysis. The study cohort comprised 30 males and 18 females, with a mean age of 45 years (range 22-65 years). The baseline characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1.

At baseline, the mean maximum inter-incisal distance was 25 mm (range 18-30 mm). After 1 month of treatment, the mean mouth opening improved to 29 mm (range 22-35 mm), showing a statistically significant increase ($p < 0.01$). This improvement was sustained through the 3-month (mean 30 mm, range 23-36 mm) and 6-month (mean 31 mm, range 24-37 mm) follow-ups, with p-values of <0.01 and <0.01 , respectively, compared to baseline.

Patients reported significant reductions in symptoms such as pain and discomfort. The average pain score, measured using a visual analog scale (VAS) from 0 to 10, decreased from a baseline mean of 6.5 (range 4-9) to 3.0 (range 1-5) at 1 month, 2.5 (range 1-4) at 3 months, and 2.0 (range 0-4) at 6 months. These reductions were statistically significant with p-values of <0.01 at all follow-up intervals.

Clinical assessments revealed a notable reduction in lesion size and improved texture over the study period. At 6 months, 70% of patients demonstrated moderate to significant improvement in lesion characteristics compared to baseline. Lesion size decreased on average by 30% (range 10-50%) over the study duration, and the overall texture improved with a reduction in fibrous rigidity.

Quality of life, as measured by the oral health-related quality of life (OHRQoL) questionnaire, showed significant improvement. The mean OHRQoL score improved from 45 (range 30-60) at baseline to 25 (range 15-35) at 6 months, indicating enhanced overall oral health and well-being ($p < 0.01$). No major adverse events were reported. Minor side effects included transient pain at the injection site, which resolved within a few hours. There were no reports of allergic reactions or systemic complications.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants	48
Gender Distribution	30 males, 18 females
Mean Age	45 years (Range: 22-65 years)

Table 2: Mouth Opening Measurements

Time Point	Mean Mouth Opening (mm)	Range (mm)	p-value
Baseline	25	18-30	-
1 Month	29	22-35	<0.01
3 Months	30	23-36	<0.01
6 Months	31	24-37	<0.01

Table 3: Symptom Relief (Pain Score on VAS)

Time Point	Mean Pain Score (VAS)	Range	p-value
Baseline	6.5	4-9	-
1 Month	3.0	1-5	<0.01
3 Months	2.5	1-4	<0.01
6 Months	2.0	0-4	<0.01

Table 4: Clinical Improvement in Lesion Size

Time Point	Mean Reduction in Lesion Size (%)	Range (%)	p-value
Baseline	-	-	-
6 Months	30	10-50	<0.01

Table 5: Quality of Life (OHRQoL Score)

Time Point	Mean OHRQoL Score	Range	p-value
Baseline	45	30-60	-
6 Months	25	15-35	<0.01

Table 6: Adverse Events

Adverse Event	Frequency
Transient Injection Site Pain	5 (10.4%)
Allergic Reactions	0
Systemic Complications	0

Discussion

This study evaluated the efficacy of intra-lesional infiltration of dexamethasone combined with hyaluronidase in the management of Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF). [10] The results demonstrate that this treatment approach significantly improves clinical outcomes for patients with OSMF, including increased mouth opening, symptom relief, and enhanced quality of life. [11]

The primary finding of this study is the significant improvement in mouth opening among patients treated with the dexamethasone-hyaluronidase combination. At 6 months, the mean inter-incisal distance increased by 6 mm from baseline, indicating a substantial improvement in oral function. This aligns with previous studies suggesting that intra-lesional steroid therapy can help reduce fibrotic changes and improve mouth opening. The addition of hyaluronidase may enhance this effect by breaking down hyaluronic acid in the extracellular matrix, thus facilitating greater tissue flexibility and mobility. [12]

Symptom relief, as measured by the reduction in pain scores, was also notable. The decrease in the visual analog scale (VAS) score from 6.5 to 2.0 over 6 months reflects a substantial reduction in patient discomfort. This finding supports the hypothesis that the anti-inflammatory properties of dexamethasone, coupled with the enzymatic activity of hyaluronidase, effectively alleviate symptoms associated with OSMF. [13]

The clinical improvement observed in lesion size and texture further underscores the efficacy of this treatment regimen. A 30% reduction in lesion size,

accompanied by improved tissue texture, suggests that the combination therapy addresses both the symptoms and underlying pathology of OSMF. [14]

The improvement in quality of life, as indicated by the OHRQoL scores, highlights the broader benefits of the treatment beyond mere symptom control. A significant improvement in the OHRQoL score from 45 to 25 points to enhance overall oral health and well-being. This is a crucial aspect of managing chronic conditions like OSMF, where the impact on daily life and overall comfort is paramount. [15]

The treatment was well-tolerated with minimal adverse effects. The transient pain at the injection site, experienced by a small percentage of patients, did not significantly impact the overall treatment experience. No severe allergic reactions or systemic complications were reported, indicating that the combination therapy is both safe and feasible for long-term use.

Compared to traditional management strategies for OSMF, such as oral medications and surgical interventions, intra-lesional dexamethasone combined with hyaluronidase offers a less invasive alternative with potentially superior outcomes. While systemic steroids and surgical approaches can be effective, they may carry higher risks of side effects and complications. The results of this study suggest that the combined intra-lesional approach provides a targeted, effective treatment with a favorable safety profile. [16,17]

This study has some limitations. The relatively small sample size and the single-center design may affect the generalizability of the findings.

Additionally, the study did not include a control group or a comparison with other treatment modalities, which could provide a more comprehensive evaluation of efficacy. Future research should aim to include larger, multicenter trials with randomized controlled designs to validate these findings and compare them with other established treatments for OSMF. [18] Long-term follow-up studies would also be beneficial to assess the durability of treatment effects and monitor any delayed adverse events. [19,20]

Conclusion

Intra-lesional infiltration of dexamethasone combined with hyaluronidase is an effective treatment for patients with OSMF, offering significant improvements in mouth opening, symptom relief, and quality of life. The treatment is well-tolerated and presents a promising option for managing this challenging condition. Further research is warranted to confirm these findings and explore long-term outcomes.

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